

A STUDY ON TRAINING PROCEDURE AND ITS EFFECTIVENESS IN CREATIVE TEX, TIRUPUR

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Introduction:

Every organization needs trained and experienced people to perform the activities that have to be done. If the current or potential job occupant can meet this requirement, training is not important. But when this is not the case, it is necessary to elevate the skill levels and increase the versatility and adaptability of employees. When any organization arranges the training programme to the employees and workers, there must be systematic procedures to be followed from the beginning of the training to the end of the training. Then only it will ensure that the training is effectively reached to all the workers and employees to develop their personality and skills in their work or job. But in many occasion the training programme which is arranged by the employers could not serve the purpose of the employees in improving the skills and efficiency of the individuals. Hence, it is the responsibility of the management to see that whether the trainers organize the training properly and necessary attention is given by the employees during the period of training. In some of the well-established concern, the training programme is properly organized in such a way that will serve the purpose of the employers. To identify the issues and problems in the training procedures a thorough study is to be undertaken. Hence, it is inevitable to do a project on the **Training Procedure and Its Effectiveness in Creative Tex, Tirupur:**

Statement of the Problem:

In all reputed concerns, it is the practice of providing training to the newly recruited employees and workers. Based on the training and the efficiency of the employees in the training period the workers and employees are placed in various departments. But the performance of the employees is evaluated after some time by the employers or any officials empowered to evaluate the performance of the workers. The employees perform their duty allocated to them and try to make perfection in their work at a maximum level. The efficiency for the workers after training is varied from person to person. In many occasions, the skill of the workers depends on the individual commitment in their work. Some of them perform their work very normally without improving their efficiency. Due to this reason some time the employers send them out from the job. The employees say that improper training system from the management is the main reason for the inability to perform the work. In small concerns there is no separate training to the workers, which is main problem to the workers in improving the efficiency.

Need for the Study:

In many concerns, the turnover of employees is going on increasing as there is no proper training system and procedures for improving the efficiency of the employees. If the employees are given proper training at the right time, it will help to improve the efficiency of the workers simultaneously the concern can easily achieve the targets of the organization within the specified time, When the employees get training it will help them to earn more income by improving their skill. Then they will not get frustration in their work. They will be ready to work harmoniously to achieve the goal of the organization.

Objectives of the Study:

Primary Objective:

To find out the effectiveness of training to employees in CREATIVE TEX

Secondary Objectives:

- ✓ To find out whether the training programmes are helpful for individual and organizational growth or not.
- ✓ To find out the training provided by the organization is capable of meeting all the objectives of the organization or not.
- ✓ To find the problems faced by the respondents during training period.
- ✓ To offer suggestions and recommendations to solve the problem faced by the workers in CREATIVE TEX at the time of training.

Research Methodology:

Descriptive research have been undertaken in this research work to make research effective and find the results of the research work successfully.

Data Collection:

Both primary and secondary data have been collected for the research work.

Primary Data:

Primary data have been collected by framing questionnaire and interview schedule with the sample respondents. Necessary corrections, additions and deletions have been made in the questionnaire with the help of the experts and supervisor to make the research as an effective and useful to the society.

Secondary Data:

Secondary data was collected from the books and journal published in relation to training and effectiveness to the workers

Sampling Method:

In this research work respondents were selected from the total population at random by using convenient sampling method

Sample Size:

As the population for the research work in the study area is numerous. Out of total population employees, 100 employees were selected by using convenient sampling method. The sample constitutes both the female and male workers who are employed in CREATIVE TEX

Period of Study:

The research work was carried out for the period of 2 months starting from July 2016 to August 2016.

Statistical Tools:

The following are the tools, which are used for the analyzing the collected data and to find out the result of the research work to complete the research work successfully.

- ✓ Percentage method
- ✓ Mean square method
- ✓ Likert's scale method.
- ✓ Chi Square method
- ✓ Rank Correlation method

Review of Literature:

Study of jobs and skill analysis is necessary. The training thus imparted would help the employees to adjust to their job requirements (Dayal 1970). Training needs for supervisors need to be identified through careful observations, which indicate poor performance, low production, high cost, poor product quality, high scrap, spoilage,

wastage, accidents, absenteeism, and turnover (Sundaram 1970). While Building knowledge – based society and economy, particular importance in human Resources management fall on the value of human resources and management expertise (Lobanova 2009).

The day-to-day complaints and grievances also form a useful source for identifying their training needs. There are some ideologies for training methodologies, which are the bases for training effectiveness. Multinational operating in India finds that their home- tested techniques do not have the same impact here. Due to differences in culture and background business games, T-groups, case methods and workshops are not as effective in India as perhaps in Europe or America. He ends that given the Indian context, the lecture- cum- discussion method would be more useful (Basha 1971).

Table 1: Table Showing the Sex of the Respondents

Sex	Total No of Respondents	% of the Respondents
Male	80	80
Female	20	20
Total	100	100

Source: Primary data

Interpretation:

From the above table it is clearly understand that among 100 respondents 80 % of the respondents are male, while the remaining 20% of the respondents are female.

Table 2: Table Showing the Age of the Respondents

Age	Respondents		Total	Percentage %
	Men	Women		
Below 25 years	28(27.2)	6(6.8)	34	34
25to 30	20(20.8)	6(5.2)	26	26
30 to 35	24(22.4)	4(5.6)	28	28
35 and above	08(9.6)	4(2.4)	12	12
Total	80	20	100	100

Source: primary data

Interpretation:

From the above table, it is inferred that 34% of the respondents belong to the age group of below 25 years and 26% of the respondents belong to the age group 25 to 30 years, 28% of the respondents belong to the age group of 30 to 35 years where as 12% of the respondents belong to the age group of 35 years and above.

Chi-Square Test:

Null Hypothesis:

There is no significant relationship between respondents based on the sex and their age

Alternative Hypothesis:

There is significant relationship between respondents based on the sex and their age

Factor	Calculated Value X ²	Table Value	DF	Remarks
Age	2.173	7.815	3	Significant

As the calculated value of χ^2 (2.173) is less than the table of χ^2 (7.815) at 3 degree of freedom for 5 % level of significance, there is no significant relationship between the respondents based on the sex and their age. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted and concluded that there is no significant relationship between the respondents based on sex and their age

Table 3: Table Showing the Monthly Income of the Respondents

Monthly Income (Rs)	Respondents		Total	Percentage %
	Male	Female		
Below 10000	36(33.6)	06(8.4)	42	42
10000 to 20000	16(19.2)	08(4.8)	24	24
20000to 30000	12(12.8)	04(3.2)	16	16
30000 and above	16(14.2)	02(3.6)	18	18
Total	80	20	100	100

Source: Primary data

Interpretation:

From the above table its understood that 42% of the respondents earn monthly income less than Rs.10000, 24% of the respondents earn Rs10000 to Rs20000 per month , 16% of the respondents earn Rs20000 to Rs30000and 18% of the respondents earn Rs.30000 and above per month.

Null Hypothesis:

There is no significant relationship between respondents based on the sex and their income

Alternative Hypothesis:

There is significant relationship between respondents based on the sex and their income

Factor	Calculated Value χ^2	Table Value	DF	Remarks
Income	4.711	7.815	3	Significant

As the calculated value of χ^2 (4.711) is less than the table of χ^2 (7.815) at 3 degree of freedom for 5 % level of significance, there is no significant relationship between the respondents based on the sex and their income. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted and concluded that there is no significant relationship between the respondents based on sex and their income

Table 4: Table Showing the Work Experience of the Respondents

Work Experience	Respondents		Total	Percentage %
	Male	Female		
Below 5 years	12(12)	03(3)	15	15
5-10 years	23(23.2)	06(5.8)	29	29
10-15 years	32(31.2)	07(7.8)	39	39
15-20 years	07(6.4)	01(1.6)	08	08
Above 20 years	06(7.2)	03(1.8)	09	09
Total	80	20	100	100

Source: Primary Data:

Experience makes perfection and also increases the efficiency of the individual which will help the organization to achieve the goals and complete the works efficiently. Hence a survey was undertaken to know the experiences of the respondents.

Interpretation:

The above table shows that among 100 respondents 39% of the respondents have 10-15 years experience, 29% of the respondents have 5-10 years experience, 15% of the respondents have below 5 years experience, while the remaining 9% of the respondents have more than 20 years experience.

Null Hypothesis:

There is no significant relationship between respondents based on the sex and their work experience

Alternative Hypothesis:

There is significant relationship between respondents based on the sex and their work experience

Factor	Calculated Value χ^2	Table Value	DF	Remarks
Gender	1.39	9.488	4	Significant

As the calculated value of χ^2 (1.39) is less than the table of χ^2 (9.488) at 4 degree of freedom for 5 % level of significance, there is no significant relationship between the respondents based on the sex and their work experience. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted and concluded that there is no significant relationship between the respondents based on sex and their work experience.

Findings:

- ✓ The company has more number of male workers than female workers.
- ✓ Most of the respondents belong to the age group of 25-30 years
- ✓ Major portion of the respondents have studied up to school level.
- ✓ Majority of the respondents both in male and female employees are married
- ✓ Major portion of the employees earn a monthly income less than Rs.10000 per month.
- ✓ Majority of the respondents have the experience of 10 -15 years in their work.
- ✓ Most of the respondents are permanent employees in the company.
- ✓ Most of the respondents are satisfied with the working environment prevailing in the company.
- ✓ Maximum number of employees feels that their skill is utilized to the fullest extent possible.
- ✓ Most of the employees feel that the training needs identified by the superior are proper and appropriate.
- ✓ The employees agrees that the needs identified each year matches with the organizational goal.
- ✓ The employee is satisfied that the superior discusses with them while, identifying any training needs.
- ✓ Most of the employees feel that the identified training needs are relevant to their job.
- ✓ The employees are satisfied about organization takes care of all emergency training needs that arise from time to time.
- ✓ Most employees are dissatisfied about the course materials provided by the organization for the training program.
- ✓ The ability of the trainees to communicate in the training program is not good.
- ✓ Most of the employees agree that they have all freedom and encouragement to ask and clear doubts in training program.
- ✓ The administrative arrangement made for training and interest of training program is very good.
- ✓ The training activities of the organization are easy to follow and the organization have a systematical procedure for the evaluation of training.
- ✓ Most of the respondents informed they are satisfied with the training facilities in the company
- ✓ Major portion of the respondents feel that training provided by the organization is capable of meeting all objectives

Findings from Chi-Square Test:

- ✓ There is a significant relationship between the respondents based on sex and their age
- ✓ There is no significant relationship between the respondents based on sex and educational qualifications of the respondents.
- ✓ There is no significant relationship between the respondents based on sex and their marital status.
- ✓ There is no significant relationship between the respondents based on sex and their income
- ✓ There is no significant relationship between the respondents based on sex and their work experience.
- ✓ There is no significant relationship between the respondents based on sex and the nature of job
- ✓ There is no significant relationship between the respondents based on sex and their level of satisfaction regarding the organizational environment.
- ✓ There is no significant relationship between the respondents based on educational qualifications and their opinion regarding the training provided in the company.
- ✓ There is no significant relationship between the respondents based on sex and their level of satisfaction regarding satisfaction regarding the time provided for training.

Findings from Rank Correlation Test:

As there is a positive correlation, the respondents based on the sex have similar attitudes in stating the problems faced by them at the time of training.

Suggestions:

- ✓ The organization should take efforts and provide adequate course materials for the training program.
- ✓ Arrangements should be made by the organization to improve communication among employees in the training program.
- ✓ The time provided for training is not sufficient. So enough time should be provided for training activities.
- ✓ The organization should implement various steps and measures to improve the administrative arrangement made for training.
- ✓ The organisation should also allow the workers to participate with their superior in identifying the training needs.
- ✓ Some of the employees informed that the training timing is not adequate to get thorough knowledge; hence the management of CREATIVE TEX may if possible try to increase the timing for training.
- ✓ Few respondents informed that that they face problems from the seniors. Hence the management may try to solve such type of issues within the organization.
- ✓ Some of the respondents gave bad opinion about the overall training programme. Hence the management may try to improve the training programme in the future periods which will help to retain the experienced workers to achieve the ultimate goal of the organization.

Conclusion:

The previous studies based on institutional training programmes do not evaluate how they benefit to the industries concerned. The institutional training programmes do not concentrate on future needs of individual organizations, which vary in environment and production process. So, the environmental condition among the centers of learning

and applications of learning are not homogeneous. Further, the impact of training depends on the caliber of the participants, which varies from individual to individual. The previous studies carried out have evaluated the impact of training on the level of workforce that is 'executives' or 'management trainees' or 'students of management' level only. Thus, it may be the impact of managerial caliber of that level of workforce but in a manufacturing unit, most of the works are 'group work', which needs smooth 'work culture' of total workforce.

Thus, the current study deals with the pre-training arrangements process and explains the interdependent elements of 'planning part' consisting of training need identification and selection of right participants, the 'execution part' which is composed of suitable methods and appropriate techniques. Training coordinators link the two parts of training process. This sequential arrangement is analyzed and then the impacts of training on self- needs attainment are considered. The details regarding self-goals towards training, advancement of knowledge by training and performance change of self due to training for the levels of employees and supervisors has been studied. Training the human resources is more important in order to utilize man power effectively. Modernization needs more training for employees in order to meet necessities for improving quality, production etc. So training is an important area where manpower is molded and retained to work better.

The training activities in CREATIVE TEX have been studied in depth. Through the questionnaire from the respondent, the researcher had collected valuable data with regard to the subject matter. Though there are problems in the training programme of in CREATIVE TEX, It is clearly seen in this organization that the personnel department effectively implementing the training and development activities in general.

References:

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